

A rapid and low cost sensitive method of on-spot detection of RDX (Cyclonite)

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Abstract : A simple and sensitive method of detection of RDX is reported. The method is rapid and economic and can be suitably utilized for the on-spot detection of RDX.

Keywords : Chromotropic acid, RDX.

RDX is a high explosive used extensively for military purposes^{1,2} and more recently for world wide terrorist activities. Seizure of explosives is a routine exercise for military intelligence and criminal investigation department. RDX can easily be detected and quantitated in the laboratory using TLC, GC-TEA, HPLC, GC-MS or FTIR instruments^{1,2}. RDX can also be detected visually or colorimetrically using chromotropic acid in presence of conc. H₂SO₄. But the reagents or the instruments are not readily available making on spot detection of RDX extremely difficult. Thus, a rapid and sensitive method for on spot detection (not spot test) of RDX from the numerous seized samples from distant places may be of great help for the investigating authorities. The present communication outlines a simple and low cost method of on spot detection of RDX which can be performed by non-technical personnel like police, military or even common people without the help of an equipped laboratory.

Experimental

Fresh (formaldehyde free) milk (cow, buffalo and goat) was collected directly from local sources during milching. RDX was obtained from High Energy Materials Research Laboratory, Pune. Formaldehyde (A.R., B.D.H., England), acetone (HPLC grade), FeCl₃, CuSO₄.5H₂O, MnCl₂.4H₂O, CoSO₄.7H₂O, (CH₃COO)₂Pb.3H₂O, H₂SO₄ (E. Merck's, A.R. quality) were used in the experiment. The experimen-

tal solution of RDX containing 1 mg/ml in acetone was prepared from a stock solution containing 0.05017 g of RDX in 50 ml acetone. 0.1 ml of the experimental solution was dried and the content was dissolved in 10 ml conc. H₂SO₄. 2 ml (2×10^{-5} g) of this solution was added drop by drop to 10 ml of milk slowly by the side of the test tube. Conc. H₂SO₄ converts milk into casein which in presence of CH₂O (RDX + H₂SO₄) gave a polymeric milk casein agglomerate on the top of the solution. The color of the agglomerate were different with different metal ions like Cu²⁺ (redish brown), Mn²⁺ (dark brown), Pb²⁺ (dark brown), Co²⁺ (dark brown) etc. (conc. $\approx 5 \times 10^{-3}$ g in each case) but a beautiful blue violet polymeric milk casein agglomerate resulted in presence of FeCl₃ (1 ml from the stock solution of 0.50246 g in 100 ml water) at the top of the solution which was more or less colorless (slightly yellowish in color due to FeCl₃ solution). Slight impurities like Cu²⁺, Mn²⁺, Pb²⁺, Co²⁺ (conc. range 2×10^{-5} g – 5×10^{-5} g) did not interfere. There is no possibility of the presence of NH₂ or phenolic OH group in RDX but these groups even if present would have no effect on the color of the agglomerate in presence of conc. H₂SO₄. The reaction is simple, safe but destructive in nature. The experiments were repeated more than ten times to check the reproducibility of the result. Hand swabs containing RDX are of little concern to the forensic scientist, as RDX is generally used in IED (Improved Explosive Device) like bombs and detonated by

suitable devices from a distance. But the test is equally suitable for hand swab containing RDX. Hand swab was dissolved in acetone and the solution was dried. RDX thus obtained was dissolved in conc. H_2SO_4 . The experimental solution was used as before. RDX from explosive debris can also be detected by extracting RDX and other organics by acetone. Acetone extract was dried and dissolved in conc. H_2SO_4 and the test was carried out in the same way as before. Due to heterogeneity of the agglomerate, absorption measurements in solution was not possible but the absorption measurements of the blue violet polymeric milk casein was done using Desaga HPTLC system. The parameters were : Desaga CD 60 densitometer, the length of the light beam was 8 mm, the height of the light beam was 0.2 mm, scan range was 450 nm to 700 nm. The thin film of the sample was placed on a glass plate and scanned against a thin film of the standard milk casein produced similarly.

Results and discussion

All the analytical techniques which are suitable for the detection and quantitation of HCHO are also suitable for the detection and quantitation of RDX as RDX decomposes to HCHO in presence of conc. H_2SO_4 (usually 16 N or more). The reaction is

Formaldehyde converts casein and other products into inert hard horny masses (artificial ivories)³. Formaldehyde produces a deep blue violet color with milk in presence of concentrated H_2SO_4 (producing casein) and FeCl_3 . The test was reported to be sensitive to 1 parts of formaldehyde in 2×10^5 parts of milk⁴. The test was used by the law enforcing authority of England to detect formaldehyde used as preservative in milk. The sensitiveness is expected to be better in case of RDX (from eq. (1)). In the present experiment, final concentration of RDX used was 2×10^{-5} g. The results agree with the literature⁴. The reaction known as Acree-Rosenheim reaction⁵ is similar to Hopkins-Cole or glyoxalic acid reaction for tryptophan³. The nature of the complex is not known but the reaction is characteristics of the indole ring. Since tryptophan is the only amino acid in the milk proteins which contain indole ring, the test is indicative of the presence of tryptophan³.

It is a highly sensitive qualitative test for on-spot detec-

tion (but not quantitation) of RDX. The test for RDX can be carried out in absence of an equipped laboratory as the test requires a few ml of fresh milk (5–10 ml), few drops of conc. H_2SO_4 and 2–3 drops of FeCl_3 solution (even a minute amount of rust can bring color). The cost involved is negligible. RDX can also be detected in the similar way using tryptophan

To understand the nature of the violet color milk casein polymer, the polymer was pressed between two filter papers to remove water as far as possible. The polymer was scanned against casein polymer obtained similarly (without adding CH_2O and FeCl_3) as back ground. The absorption maximum was found to be 583 nm. But nothing positive can be said about the nature of the complex. It is to be noted that tryptophan when mixed with RDX and concentrated H_2SO_4 gives a red colored complex in presence of FeCl_3 having an absorption maximum at 451.3 nm. But the color of the casein polymeric complex is different indicating that the formation of casein polymers forming different linkages by CH_2O . The method is equally applicable to HMX (which we did not study)

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